

EVALUATION OF TILLAGE PRACTICES FOR IN SITU MOISTURE CONSERVATION UNDER DIFFERENT CROPPING SYSTEMS

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Abstract

Field experiment was conducted for evaluation of tillage practices for *in situ* moisture conservation under different cropping systems on AICRP dry land field Marathwada Agricultural University, Parbhani. For tillage practices plowing across the slope at 10 cm depth T_1 (control), plowing across the slope at 20 cm depth T_2 , plowing across the slope at 30 cm depth T_3 , plowing across the slope at 40 cm depth T_4 and cropping systems, sowing sole cotton across the slope C_1 , cotton + soybean (1:1) ratio across the slope C_2 and sole soybean across the slope C_3 . From experiment it was found that, for *in situ* soil moisture conservation ploughing across the slope at 30cm and 40 cm depth was found more effective in moisture retention as compared to the remaining 10cm and 20cm tillage practices. Tillage practices of ploughing across the slope at 30cm and 40 cm depth was found better in forms of moisture retention and biometric parameters of growth of soybean and cotton. The highest yield of the soybean and cotton i.e. 18.57 q/ha and 19.55 q/ha respectively were observed in the 30cm deep tillage practice T_3 as compared to the remaining tillage practices.

Keyword: Tillage, *In situ*, Soybean, Biometric Parameter

Introduction

Water is one of the most vital natural resource for sustaining life on earth. Now a day, erratic behavior of rainfall & uneven distribution of rainfall in time & space poses the problem of moisture stress condition to the crops during its growing period. To overcome moisture stress condition, *in-situ* soil & water conservation practices plays vital important role in moisture conservation. Keeping in view, field experiment was carried with following objectives, To study the effect

of cultivation practices on *in-situ* soil moisture conservation under different cropping system and To study effect of crop response under different cultivation practices.

Technique in brief:

Field experiment was conducted at AICRP on Dry land Agriculture research farm, Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth Parbhani. Experiment was laid out as per split plot design. The details of experiment were as follows.

Experimental details:

Crop and variety	:	Cotton - Banny Bt
	:	Soybean -MAUS 61-2
Year of commencement	:	2022-2023
Land Slope	:	1.45%
Soil type	:	Medium deep
Plot size	:	20 m x 7.2m =144m ² (Length-20m, width- 7.20m)
Spacing of sowing	:	Cotton 120cm X 45 cm
	:	Soybean 30 cm X 5 cm
Other details	:	i) Date of sowing : 17/7/2022
	:	ii) Fertilizer doses: 120:60:60 & 30:60:30
	:	iii) Date of Harvesting of Soybean: 4/11/2022
	:	iv) Date of picking: 6/11/2022, 21/11/2022
	:	v) Period of soil moisture sample: 10Sept. to 14oct 2022

Physical and chemical properties of soil of experimental soil

A	Mechanical composition		
1	Coarse sand	Present	6.58
2	Fine sand	Present	10.30
3	Clay	Present	54.40
4	Silt	Present	21.44
5	Bulk Density	Gm/cc	1.34
6	Infiltration rate	Cm/hr	3.40
B	Chemical composition		
1	Ph		8.02
2	Ec	dSm-1	0.16
3	Organic carbon	Present	0.62
4	Caco ₃	g/kg	5.7
5	Available N	Kg/ha	135.6
6	Available P	Kg/ha	4
7	Available K	Kg/ha	829.4

Main treatmentT₁-Ploughing across the slope at 10 cm depth. (Control)T₂- Ploughing across the slope at 20 cm depthT₃- Ploughing across the slope at 30 cm depthT₄- Ploughing across the slope at 40 cm depth**B) Sub treatment**C₁-Sole CottonC₂-Cotton + Soybean (1:2)C₃-Sole Soybean.**Material and methods:****Moisture content**

For the measurement of soil moisture content in soil regime from treated field, soil samples were collected with the help of screw auger at 15 cm, 30 cm and 45 cm depth. These samples were then oven dried for 24 hr at the temperature of 105^oC. The percentage moisture content observed by using following formula.

$$\% \text{ Moisture content (dry basis)} = \left(\frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_2} \times 100 \right)$$

Where,

W₁ = Weight of wet sample (gm)W₂ = Weight of dry sample (gm)**Biometric Observations:**

Replication wise five plants were selected and biometric observations like height of plant; number of branches and number of bolls/ pods of each plant were recorded. Finally the average biometric observations through out the growth period were recorded

Crop Yield.

Replication wise harvesting were carried out for both the crops i.e. cotton and soybean and per- hectore yield of cotton and soybean were recorded.

Results and Discussion:

Field experiment was conducted at AICRP on dry land research farm Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth Parbhani. During kharif 2011-12. The experiment consisted of main treatments depth of plowing across the slope at various depths i.e 10 cm (T₁), 20 cm, (T₂) 30 cm, (T₃) and 40 cm, (T₄).

Table 1: Mean soil moisture content as influenced by tillage practices under different cropping systems, kharif-2022-23

Treatments	% Soil moisture content			
	15cm	30cm	45cm	mean
T ₁	8.10	9.51	10.09	9.23 (-)
T ₂	10.97	10.81	11.65	11.14 (20.69%)
T ₃	11.42	14.24	13.98	13.21 (43.12%)
T ₄	13.46	12.27	11.45	12.36 (33.91%)
Treatment	SE	CD		
	0.20	0.60		
Depth	0.16	0.48		
Treatment x Depth	0.32	0.97		
Total rain fall received during 10 Sept to 14 Oct 2011 = 114.2 mm				

Data in the Table 1 revealed that among tillage practices ploughing up to 30 cm depth T₃ gives significantly higher soil moisture content (13.21 %) than rest of the treatments. It was also observed that treatment T₄ followed to T₃. Among the interaction between tillage practices and depth of soil moisture content, depth at 30 cm in

treatment T₃ the soil moisture content was recorded higher (14.24%) than 15 cm and 45 cm. depths. As compared to control treatment T₁, the per cent soil moisture content in T₃ treatment (43.12 %) was recorded and in T₄ (33.91 %) and T₂ (20.69 %) respectively.

Table 2 : Average biometric observations of cotton as influenced by tillage practices under different cropping systems, kharif-2022-23

Treatments	Height of plant (cm)	Number of branches	Number of bolls
T ₁	49.00	10.33	17.00
T ₂	50.00	12.66	21.00
T ₃	55.00	15.60	33.66
T ₄	56.00	15.66	32.33
SE	1.55	0.31	1.89
CD at 5% level	5.37	1.10	6.55

Data pertaining in the Table 2. revealed that the performances of sole cotton crop in term of plant height, number of branches, are found slightly better but in terms of Number of picked bolls per plant was

found significantly superior in T₃ treatment (33.66) than the rest of the treatments. It was also found that the treatment T₄ is followed by to T₃.

Table 3 : Average biometric observations of soybean as influenced by tillage Practices under different cropping systems, kharif-2022-23

Treatments	Height of plant (cm)	Number of branches	Number of pods
T ₁	31.00	6.00	19.00
T ₂	36.00	7.00	31.00
T ₃	42.00	9.00	34.00
T ₄	39.00	8.00	33.00
SE	2.10	0.64	1.62
CD at 5% level	7.26	2.23	5.61

From Table 3. It was found that the performances of sole soybean crop in term of plant height, number of branches, and number of pods per plant was found significantly superior in T₃ treatment (42cm 9 and 34.00) than the rest of the treatments. In treatment T₃ maximum height

of plant and number of branches were recorded which is followed by treatment T₄ and T₂. Minimum height of plant and number of branches were recorded in treatment T₂.

Table 4: Yield of Cotton (banny Bt) and Soybean (MAUS 61-2) as influenced by tillage practices under different cropping systems ,kharif-2022-23

Treatments	Sole cotton kg/plot q/ha		Inter Cropping				Sole soybean Kg/plot q/ha		Stalk yield q/ha	
			Cotton		Soybean					
			Kg/plot	q/ha	Kg/plot	q/ha			soybean	cotton
T ₁	5.83	12.15	4.15	8.65	4.89	10.20	5.06	10.55	9.32	26.25
T ₂	6.07	12.65	6.04	10.60	5.28	11.00	6.56	13.67	10.15	26.17
T ₃	9.36	19.55	7.05	14.70	6.18	13.72	8.91	18.57	16.67	30.62
T ₄	9.38	19.50	6.15	12.13	6.38	13.30	7.86	16.37	14.52	29.12

Table 5: Seed Cotton grain eq.Yield (q/ha) as affected by Tillage treatments and Cropping Systems ,Kharif 2022-23

Treatments	Cropping Systems			
	C1	C2	C3	Mean
T1	12.15	13.87	5.40	10.47
T2	12.65	16.23	6.97	11.95
T3	19.55	21.72	9.50	16.92
T4	19.50	19.32	8.37	15.73
Mean	15.96	17.78	7.56	13.77
	SE	CD at 5% level		
Treatments	0.14	0.40		
Cropping Systems	0.12	0.35		
Treatments X Cropping Systems	0.24	0.70		

From Table 5, It was found that mean seed cotton grain equivalent yield (16.92 q/ha) in tillage treatment T₃, is ploughing across the slope at 30 cm depth was recorded significantly superior than rest of the treatments. It was also found that among the cropping systems grain equivalent seed cotton yield recorded significantly higher (17.78 q/ha

) in inter cropping systems of cotton + soybean (1:2) ratio. Among the interaction between tillage treatments and cropping systems it was found that ploughing across the slope at 30 cm depth with inter cropping system of cotton + soybean (1:2) ratio recorded higher seed cotton grain yield (21.72 q/ha) than rest of the combinations.

Table: 6 MEAN GMR, NMR, and B: C Ratio as affected by Tillage Practices and Cropping Systems.

A.Tillage Practices	Seed cotton yield q/ha	Cost of cultivation Rs/ha	GMR Rs/ha	NMR Rs/ha	B:C Ratio
T1	10.47	36677.35	34551	-2126.35	1:0.94
T2	11.95	36677.35	39435	2757.65	1:1.07
T3	16.92	36677.35	55836	19158.65	1:1.52
T4	15.73	36677.35	51909	15231.65	1:1.41
B.Cropping Systems					
Sole Cotton (C1)	15.96	36677.35	52668	15990.65	1:1.43
Cotton + Soybean(1:1) C2	17.78	36677.35	58674	21996.65	1:1.59
Sole Soybean C3	14.79	21918.52	24995	3076.48	1:1.14

(Market prices considered for GMR as, Cotton, Rs 33/Kg.and for soybean Rs 16.90/k

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